

Analysis of soil water regime in the soil with applied biochar using field scale hydrological model SWAP

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The main objective of this study was to analyze the impact of the biochar application on the soil water regime using the SWAP hydrological model. To reach this goal we will calibrate a field-scale model SWAP based on the existing data from a biochar field experiment located in Dolná Malanta (Nitra, Slovakia). The statistical analysis was conducted by the model sensitivity analysis (index of agreement, Nash Sutcliffe efficiency and percent bias/deviation). Index of agreement (d) was 0.938 and 0.933 for Control (pure silty loam soil) and B20 (treatment with applied biochar in the rate of 20 t ha⁻¹), respectively. Results of the sensitivity analysis also demonstrated that the model had reliable sensitivity to daily precipitation changes. The simulated water regime corresponds to the observed data of soil moisture and it was higher on the treatment with applied biochar (B20) during the whole simulation period (from April to September 2019) associated with the higher water storage on B20 treatment.

KEY WORDS: SWAP model, model calibration, biochar amended soil, water storage

Introduction

Without sufficient water, plants are threatened by drought and malnourishment (Liu et al., 2017; Bolla et al., 2025). Therefore, improving soil's ability to retain water for crop growth and development is a critical current issue that should be addressed. Biochar, due to its durable nature and high porosity, using as soil amendment, has been suggested as an ecological approach for carbon sequestration with the potential to mitigate the harmful impacts of extreme climate variability (Mukherje and Lal, 2013; Longbottom et al., 2022). Numerous studies reported positive ecosystem benefits of biochar application (Thao et al., 2025), e.g., increased water retention (Brockhoff et al. 2010; Karhu et al., 2011; Abrol et al., 2016; Shyam et al., 2025), increased plant growth and reduced evapotranspiration (Guo et al., 2024). These changes can be associated with response to change in soil moisture (Novák et al., 2012; Vitková et al., 2020; Vitková et al., 2021), soil hydro-physical (Castellini et al. 2015; Hlaváčiková et al., 2016; Makó et al. 2020, Botková et al., 2023) and soil physiochemical properties (Ajayi and Horn, 2016) as altered by biochar application. Existing research on biochar application in the study area has predominantly concentrated on evaluating field and laboratory measurements derived from soil samples. In contrast, process-based approaches employing hydrological models have received limited attention, despite their

potential to address critical knowledge gaps and to extrapolate experimental findings across spatial and temporal scales (Libahova et al., 2024). This underutilisation leaves a significant gap in our understanding.

Hydrological modeling in soil science is a tool for predicting the effect of soil water balance components on the ecosystem services (de Jong Van Lier et al., 2024). Soil hydrological models, like the Soil Water Atmosphere Plant model (SWAP) are commonly run from profile- up to field-scales. The SWAP model focuses on the soil water regime and believed to be more precise in describing transport of water, solutes and heat transport in the vadose zone in interaction with vegetation development (Kroes et al., 2017). In a process-based approach (de Jong Van Lier et al., 2013) it describes a domain from the top of canopy into the groundwater which may be in interaction with a surface water system (Kroes et al., 2017). Also, the soil input data of those models allows incorporation of management practices, thus, the outputs can be used as references for larger scale models such as SWAT+.

Hydrological models require the quantitative description of fundamental soil hydraulic properties, namely, water retention curves and hydraulic conductivity functions (de Jong Van Lier et al., 2024). Those functions are presented as a set of equations with soil-specific parameters (Madi et al., 2018). The performance of the model is closely related to the quality of the input parameters (Wang et al.,

2020). Due to measurement errors, intrinsic variability between samples, or inadequacy of the mathematical equation to mimic the physical phenomenon there can be uncertainty of the parameter estimates (de Jong Van Lier et al., 2024). Therefore, obtaining parameters as accurate as possible through observation or estimation is very important for improving water regime simulation accuracy. Sensitivity analysis helps to identify parameters to which the model outputs are sensitive and determine the optimal parameter adjustment strategy (Wang et al., 2020).

The aim of this study is to analyze the effect of the biochar application as a soil amendment on soil water regime using a process-based hydrological model SWAP.

Material and methods

Description of the experimental site

The biochar field experiment located in Dolná Malanta (Nitra, Slovakia) (latitude 48°19'23.41", longitude 18°09'0.7") was established in Spring 2014 to study the impact of biochar application in the rates 0, 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹ on the greenhouse gas emissions (Kotuš et al., 2022), soil physical and hydro-physical properties (Igaz et al., 2018; Toková et al., 2020), soil quality and crop yields (Vitková et al., 2017). The soil was classified as Haplic Luvisol according to World Reference Base (FAO, 2014) and has silty loam soil texture. The site was used for conventional agricultural production prior to establishment of the experiment. In the studied year 2019

a common field crop was grown at the site; namely corn (*Zea mays* L.). Biochar used in this field experiment was made from paper fiber sludge mixed grain husks in a 1:1 ratio (according to their weight). The feedstock was processed by pyrolysis at 550°C for 30 minutes in a Pyreg reactor (Pyreg GmbH, Görhe, Germany) and provided by Sonnenerde company (Austria) as a final commercial product with fraction size up to 5 mm (Horák et al., 2021). The biochar was incorporated in the soil with rakes. For this study the following experimental treatments were used (Table 1).

SWAP model set up – input data

We applied the SWAP model, version 4.2.0 to assess the soil water content dynamics in biochar amended and controlled fields (Kroes et al., 2017). The basic set up of the SWAP model consists of the main SWAP file (*.swp file), the weather data file (*.met file) and the crop file (*.crp file).

For this study we used daily meteorological data (such as precipitation, temperature, radiation etc.) from the nearest meteorological station (Malanta, Slovakia). The required format for daily weather data for SWAP model is shown in Fig. 1. We indicated potential evapotranspiration (E_{tref}) as a missing value by -99.9 value (Fig. 1) according to the OPTAIN protocol (Farkas et al., 2022). Table 2 presents monthly precipitation and mean air temperature in the year 2019.

The SWAP model employs the Richards equation for calculating the water transport within the soil – plant – atmosphere system. The Mualem – van Genuchten

Table 1. Experimental treatments

Experimental treatments	Replicates	Treatment acronym	Application rate [t ha ⁻¹]
Control soil (without biochar)	3	Control	0
Biochar-amended soil	3	B20	20

Fig. 1. a) SWAP meteorological input data in daily resolution, b) Meteorology section in the main *.swp file.

Table 2. Monthly precipitation and mean air temperature in 2019

	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	VII.	VIII.	IX.	X.	XI.	XII.
Air temperature [°C]	-3.5	0.9	5.0	9.4	9.3	18.7	18.0	18.4	12.6	8.7	5.0	-0.1
Precipitation [mm]	54.8	27.4	22.4	21.4	134.8	29.0	52.2	64.0	52.8	17.8	95.4	53.4

relations, with a modification near saturation, describes the soil hydraulic functions (Kroes et al., 2017). Table 3 and Table 4 describe the soil profile and the three soil layers and for each sublayer, we defined dry bulk density (BD) and the saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_{SAT}) (Toková et al., 2023; Igaz et al., 2021).

Pressure plate apparatus was used to determine water content at specific pressure potentials (0, 5.5, 20, 55.12, 100, 300 and 1500 kPa). Following that, the RETC (RETention Curve) program (van Genuchten et al., 1991) was used to fit residual water content (Θ_{RES}) and the shaping parameters α and n of the soil water retention curves for both experimental treatments. The soil water retention curve (pF curve in logarithmic scale) was constructed according to the van Genuchten model.

The crop section (Fig. 2a) defines the crop rotation scheme for the modelled period and the name of the *.crp files with plant data. We used plant data in separate file from a SWAP crop database. Free flux bottom boundary conditions were used at the bottom of the soil profile (Fig. 2b).

SWAP model – calibration

In our study we used soil water content measurements from disturbed soil samples from the upper 10 cm (conducted biweekly during vegetation period of the corn in total 13 sampling events) as a reference data for SWAP model calibration. We also cross validated those data with the corresponding soil water retention curves. For

the soft-calibration process we used RSWAP (Shore, 2023), which is an R-package designed for verifying and soft-calibrating the SWAP model.

Statistical analyses

The evaluation of the model performance was done according to Moriasi et al. (2015) using statistical indicators, such as the index of agreement (d), Nash Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) and percent bias/deviation (PBIAS). For visualization of the retention curves and the water regime we used OriginPro 2025 software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, USA).

Results and discussion

The results show that the calibration of the model depends on the quality and quantity of given reference data obtained from field measurements (Fig. 3). Model calibration involved perturbing the van Genuchten – Mualem parameters (Table 5 and Table 6) to minimize discrepancies between the observed and simulated soil water contents (Fig. 3).

In principle, during calibration the retention curve data should be changed in such a way as to keep points such as field capacity (Θ_{FC}) and wilting point (Θ_{WP}) as close as possible to the original measurements. Based on the quality and quantity of the given data, we were unable to fully adhere to this principle (Fig. 4). The pF curves for the calibrated values (Fig. 4) were in rather good agreement with the initial measurements in the saturation

Table 3. Vertical description of the soil profile for the Control treatment

Layers	Horizons [cm]	BD [mg cm^{-3}]	K_{SAT} [cm day^{-1}]
1 st	0-10	1420.0	39.12
2 nd	15-20	1454.4	15.11
3 rd	40-45	1497.7	1.26

Table 4. Vertical description of the soil profile for the B20 treatment

Layers	Horizons [cm]	BD [mg cm^{-3}]	K_{SAT} [cm day^{-1}]
1 st	0-10	1330.0	188.4
2 nd	15-20	1454.4	15.11
3 rd	40-45	1497.7	1.26

Fig. 2. a) Crop rotation scheme in the main *.swp file, b) Bottom boundary conditions in the main *.swp file.

Fig. 3. Simulation of the soil water regime before and after calibration on Control and B20 treatments vs observed data.

Table 5. Percentual changes in the van Genuchten parameters (namely the θ_{RES} , residual water content; θ_{SAT} , saturated water content; α and n , retention curve shaping parameters; K_{SAT} , saturated hydraulic conductivity; BD , dry bulk density) in the 1st layer during calibration on Control treatment

	VG parameters	Calibrated	Change [%]
θ_{RES} [$\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$]	0.07 (fitted)	0.05	↓ 28.57
θ_{SAT} [$\text{cm}^3 \text{cm}^{-3}$]	0.46 (measured)	0.45	↓ 2.17
α	1.76 (fitted)	0.08	↓ 95.45
n	1.09 (fitted)	1.26	↑ 15.60
K_{SAT} [cm day^{-1}]	39.12 (measured)	200.00	↑ 411.25
BD [mg cm^{-3}]	1420.00 (measured)	1420.00	0

Table 6. Percentual changes in the van Genuchten parameters (namely the θ_{RES} , residual water content; θ_{SAT} , saturated water content; α and n , retention curve shaping parameters; K_{SAT} , saturated hydraulic conductivity; BD , dry bulk density) in the 1st layer during calibration on B20 treatment

	VG parameters	Calibrated	Change [%]
θ_{RES} [$\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$]	0.26 (fitted)	0.02	↓ 92.31
θ_{SAT} [$\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$]	0.47 (measured)	0.47	0
α	0.31 (fitted)	0.08	↓ 74.19
n	1.34 (fitted)	1.20	↓ 10.45
K_{SAT} [$\text{cm} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$]	188.40 (measured)	300.40	↑ 59.45
BD [$\text{mg} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$]	1330.00 (measured)	1330.00	0

(pF close to 0) and wilting point (pF 4.18), but differed strongly from the initial data in the range between pF 1.5 and pF 3.5. This discrepancy may be attributed to

the spatio-temporal variability of soil hydraulic properties and the fact that water retention measurements were obtained from undisturbed, small soil cores.

Consequently, the measured values may not fully represent field-scale conditions. Table 5 and Table 6 presents that the saturated hydraulic conductivity increased during calibration, most probably because we did not use macropore option in the model even if there were probably macropores in the root zone. Fitted values (residual water content and shape parameters) were also changed during the calibration process (Table 5 and Table 6). Directly measured saturated water content (θ_{SAT}) was not significantly changed (Table 5 and Table 6).

Table 7 and Table 8 presents the evaluation of the model performance before and after calibration according to Moriasi et al. (2015) evaluation criteria. The ideal case would be to have all existing data for modelling purposes. However, in our case the Malanta field experiment was

not conducted for modelling purposes. We used low quality and quantity input data for SWAP model calibration and water regime simulation. According to the goodness-of-fit statistics (Moriasi et al., 2015), simulation of the soil water regime for both Control and B20 were successfully calibrated (Table 8).

Visual evaluation shows that the model responds well to the precipitation data, the timing of the peaks is well reproduced. The simulated water regime (Fig. 5) on B20 treatments is higher compared to the Control treatment that corresponds to the observed data (Fig. 7). Based on the changes in the water balance components, SWAP calculates changes in the water storage (Table 9). The initial and the final water storage was higher on B20 treatment compared to Control (Table 9) during simulation. Our results are in line with other studies.

Fig. 4. Comparison of the measured data with the pF curves constructed from the calibrated values according the van Genuchten model on the Control and B20 treatments.

Table 7. Evaluation of the model performance according to Moriasi et al. (2015) before calibration

	Control		B20	
<i>d</i>	0.351	(not satisfactory)	0.575	(not satisfactory)
NSE	- 8.960	(not satisfactory)	- 1.68	(not satisfactory)
PBIAS	86.6	(not satisfactory)	42.5	(not satisfactory)

Table 8. Evaluation of the model performance according to Moriasi et al. (2015) after calibration

	Control		B20	
<i>d</i>	0.938	(very good)	0.933	(very good)
NSE	0.716	(good)	0.71	(good)
PBIAS	8.5	(good)	7.1	(good)

Fig. 5. Simulation of the water regime on the Control and B20 treatments with total daily precipitation.

Table 9. Evaluation of the model performance according to Moriasi et al. (2015) after calibration

Simulation period	Treatment	Water storage (cm)		
		Final	Initial	Change
2019/4/01 –	Control	15.25	26.52	-11.27
2019/9/30	B20	16.65	29.57	-12.92

Positive effect of the biochar application on soil water regime and thereby alter water balance in the ecosystems were reported in previous studies (Jeffery et al. 2015; Alghamdi 2018; Yu et al. 2019). Biochar has potential to increase the soil water retention and the amount of water available to plants (Karhu et al., 2011, Blanco-Canqui 2020; Medyńska-Juraszek et al. 2021). This means that the soils amended with biochar could potentially retain more water from precipitation, which could in turn lead to an increase of crop production in non-irrigated areas (Jeffery et al. 2011) and higher irrigation efficiency in irrigated areas. According to Wang et al. (2020) high dosage ($\geq 10 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$) of high pore volume biochar can improve water retention of coarse textured soil with limited water storage capacity and may improve soil's resilience during hydrological extremes.

Conclusion

This study focuses on analysis of water regime in soil with applied biochar (dose 20 t ha^{-1}). The water regime simulation and water storage calculation were done using

SWAP (soil – water – atmosphere – plant) field-scale model. The results show increase in water content in the treatment with biochar application during the vegetation period of the corn crop in 2019. We assume, that the biochar application influenced soil pore size redistribution towards an increase of the proportion of capillary pores in the soil. Biochar directly led to an enlargement of the interval of plant available water (between field capacity and wilting point) (Fig. 4) therefore had a favorable effect on providing sufficient amount of water to plants.

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